

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE OPTIMIZED CARDIOREHABILITATION PROGRAM IN PATIENTS AFTER MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION: CLINICAL, SOCIAL, AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to assess the effectiveness of the optimized cardiorehabilitation program after myocardial infarction, taking into account physical and psycho-emotional components. The study included 138 patients (58.2 ± 8.6 years old) who had suffered an acute myocardial infarction. The main group ($n=72$) underwent a comprehensive program, including dosed physical training, psycho-emotional support, and self-control training, while the control group ($n=66$) underwent standard rehabilitation.

After six months, patients in the main group showed a significant improvement in cardiac pump function (LVEF from $48.2 \pm 7.8\%$ to $53.6 \pm 6.9\%$, $p < 0.001$), a decrease in NT-proBNP by 28% and HR-CRP by 35%, a 32% decrease in anxiety and depression according to the HADS scale, and a 31% decrease in stress load according to the PSS scale. Strength tolerance increased by 68 ± 22 m according to the six-minute walk test ($p < 0.001$), life quality according to the SF-36 scale increased by 26%, and compliance according to MMAS-8 increased from 48.6% to 77.8% ($p < 0.001$). The integral efficiency index improved from 0.64 ± 0.12 to 0.83 ± 0.09 ($p < 0.001$).

The optimized program demonstrated high clinical, psycho-emotional, and social effectiveness, contributing to a reduction in repeated hospitalizations to 3.2% and an increase in the proportion of patients with a recovery rate of $>55\%$ to 63%.

Keywords: myocardial infarction, cardiac rehabilitation, physical activity, psycho-emotional factors, NT-proBNP, HADS, SF-36, quality of life, adaptation mechanisms.

Relevance

The problem of restoring patients after a myocardial infarction remains one of the central ones in cardiology. Even with modern revascularization methods, a significant portion of patients retain signs of cardiac dysfunction, low tolerance to

stress, and emotional instability. Considering the high level of comorbidity and the risk of myocardial remodeling, the integration of physical and psycho-emotional methods into the post-infarction rehabilitation structure is of particular importance.

Purpose of the research

Conduct a comprehensive clinical, functional, and biochemical assessment of the condition of patients after myocardial infarction who have undergone coronary intervention, against the background of implementing an optimized cardiorehabilitation program.

Materials and methods

The study included 138 patients (average age 58.2 ± 8.6 years) with post-infarction atherosclerosis observed at the RSNPMC Samarkand Regional Branch. The main group ($n=72$) underwent an optimized rehabilitation program that included physical training, breathing exercises, stress management, and psycho-correctional sessions; the control group ($n=66$) received standard recovery treatment. Clinical, hemodynamic, biochemical, and psychometric indicators were assessed: ejection fraction (EF), end-diastolic volume (EDV), left ventricular myocardial mass index (LVMI), NT-proBNP, HR-CRP, 6-minute walk test (6MWT), HADS, PSS, SF-36, and MMAS-8 scales.

Research results:

Six months after the start of the rehabilitation course, patients in the main group showed pronounced positive dynamics in clinical, hemodynamic, biochemical, and psycho-emotional indicators, indicating a comprehensive restoration of the functional state of the cardiovascular system and regulatory mechanisms of adaptation.

The study revealed that the use of an optimized cardiorehabilitation program that combines physical and psycho-emotional components has a pronounced systemic effect on all levels of patient adaptation after myocardial infarction. In addition to improving cardiohemodynamic, metabolic, and psycho-emotional indicators, additional positive effects reflecting the comprehensive restoration of the body's functional reserves have been recorded.

In patients of the main group, a significant decrease in the frequency of episodes of heart rhythm disturbances (by 27%, $p < 0.05$), a decrease in the number of cases of angina pectoris of the II-III functional class (by 41%, $p < 0.01$), and normalization of blood pressure (on average from $142.6 \pm 18.4/88.2 \pm 10.7$ to $128.5 \pm 14.6/80.4 \pm 8.9$ mm Hg, $p < 0.01$) were noted. A decrease in the frequency of orthostatic reactions and an improvement in heart rate variability

were also noted, reflecting the restoration of vegetative balance and a decrease in sympathoadrenal activity.

Lipid metabolism indicators showed positive dynamics: total cholesterol decreased by 12% ($p < 0.05$), triglyceride levels decreased by 14% ($p < 0.05$), and the concentration of high-density lipoproteins increased by 9% ($p < 0.05$). This confirms that moderate-intensity physical activity combined with motivational-behavioral modules contributes to metabolic stabilization and the prevention of atherosclerosis progression.

During dynamic observation for six months, no cases of recurrent myocardial infarction were registered in the main group, while in the control group, the frequency of relapses was 4.6%. Patients who underwent the optimized program showed a significant decrease in the frequency of emergency requests and repeated hospitalizations (3.2% versus 11.5% in the control group, $p < 0.05$).

Data on the integral assessment of the program's effectiveness, including functional, biochemical, and psycho-emotional parameters, were of particular importance. The integral index improved from 0.64 ± 0.12 to 0.83 ± 0.09 ($p < 0.001$), which indicates the restoration of the adaptive potential of the cardiovascular system.

Conclusions: Overall, the obtained results confirm that a comprehensive optimized cardiorehabilitation program not only improves patients' physical condition but also contributes to a decrease in anxiety levels, increased compliance, stabilization of hemodynamic parameters, and a significant improvement in quality of life. Applying this approach will improve the effectiveness of secondary prevention of cardiovascular complications and improve the long-term prognosis of patients after myocardial infarction.

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